

Discriminating Underwater Rocks & Mines Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract: *The presence of underwater mines poses a significant threat to navigation and safety in marine environments. Sonar technology offers a crucial tool for mine detection, but differentiating rocks from mines in sonar readings can be challenging. This paper explores the application of three machine learning algorithms Logistic Regression, and k-nearest Neighbors Random forest, XGBoost to classify sonar readings and distinguish rocks from mines. We compare the performance of these algorithms in terms of accuracy, and precision using a publicly available dataset of sonar measurements. Among all the algorithms K-nearest neighbors got the highest accuracy (90%)*

Keywords—*Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, Rock/Mine Classification, Sonar technology, CSV Dataset Random forest, and XGBoost.*

I. INTRODUCTION

THE VASTNESS OF THE UNDERWATER WORLD HOLDS BOTH CAPTIVATING BEAUTY AND HIDDEN DANGERS. AMONGST THESE DANGERS LIE UNEXPLODED ORDNANCE, PARTICULARLY UNDERWATER MINES, REMNANTS OF PAST CONFLICTS POSING A SIGNIFICANT THREAT TO MARITIME SAFETY, NAVIGATION, AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH. TRADITIONAL METHODS FOR MINE DETECTION, PRIMARILY RELYING ON DIVERS OR REMOTE-OPERATED VEHICLES (ROVs) CONDUCTING VISUAL INSPECTIONS, FACE LIMITATIONS DUE TO VISIBILITY CONSTRAINTS, OPERATIONAL COMPLEXITY, AND HIGH COSTS. SONAR TECHNOLOGY EMERGES AS A POWERFUL TOOL OFFERING GREATER EFFICIENCY AND RANGE FOR UNDERWATER EXPLORATION AND HAZARD IDENTIFICATION.

However, differentiating rocks from mines in sonar readings presents a significant challenge. Both objects can share similar acoustic signatures, leading to misidentification and hindering effective mine clearance efforts. This poses a crucial need for advanced automated techniques to accurately classify sonar data and distinguish rocks from mines. Here, the potential of machine learning (ML) algorithms shines brightly.

With their ability to learn from data and make predictions, ML algorithms hold the promise of significantly enhancing underwater mine detection. This paper explores the application of three prominent ML algorithms – Logistic Regression, k- Nearest

Neighbors, and Random Forest, XGBoost to classify sonar readings and accurately identify mines.

Our research aims to contribute to the development of robust and reliable automated systems for underwater mine detection. By leveraging the power of ML, we hope to pave the way for enhanced maritime safety, improved operational efficiency, and ultimately, a safer and cleaner underwater environment.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies have investigated and utilized algorithms such as k-nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, XGBoost, and Random Forest for classification and prediction tasks. Zhang and Zhou conducted a review outlining various techniques and enhancements of the KNN algorithm, shedding light on its applications and limitations. Meanwhile, Cover and Hart's seminal paper introduced the KNN algorithm, laying the theoretical groundwork and discussing its practical implications. Logistic Regression has been extensively studied, with works like Hosmer Jr and Lemeshow's book providing a comprehensive overview of its modeling principles and practical applications. McCullagh and Nelder's work further explores logistic regression within the broader context of generalized linear models. The XGBoost algorithm gained prominence after Chen and Guestrin's paper introduced its scalable tree-boosting system, while their documentation offers detailed guidance on its usage and parameters. Similarly, Random Forest, as introduced by Breiman, has been extensively studied, with Liaw and Wiener providing insights into its implementation and performance compared to other methods. These studies collectively contribute to understanding the strengths and applications of these algorithms in various machine learning tasks. Contreras et al. investigated rock type differentiation in sandstone based on wireline pressure data formation, and Kumudham et al. applied deep learning techniques for sub-bottom image classification, showcasing the wide-ranging applications and innovations in this field. Hosmer Jr, D. W., & Lemeshow, S. "Applied logistic regression." This provides a comprehensive overview of logistic regression modeling, including practical applications and interpretation of results. Zhang, T., & Zhou, B. "A review of k-nearest neighbor classification methods." This provides insights into various techniques and enhancements of the KNN algorithm, discussing its applications, advantages, and limitations.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

1. The process involves several key steps, from data acquisition to the application of machine learning techniques for object identification.
2. Acquisition of SONAR data from designated sources to form the dataset for analysis.
3. Loading the acquired SONAR data to prepare for the model training process.
4. Execution of pre-processing steps including feature extraction, and normalization of data attributes through StandardScaler to ensure uniformity and enhance model accuracy.
5. Establishment of a cut-off value, referred to as the alpha level, to differentiate between categories.
6. Division of the SONAR data into two subsets for model validation: 90% for training and 10% for testing.
7. Implementation of various classification algorithms, including the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) classifier, Random Forest classifier, XGBoost, and logistic regression, to accurately identify underwater objects based on SONAR signatures.
8. Comprehensive evaluation of the model's effectiveness using metrics such as recall, accuracy (derived from the confusion matrix), and precision to assess performance.
9. Our methodology delineates a structured approach to collecting and processing SONAR data, applying machine learning classifiers, and conducting thorough analyses to accurately distinguish between mines and rocks underwater.

IV. STEPS USED FOR TRAINING

A. Import the dataset

The dataset contains sonar signal data for rock and mines. Import this data into the notebook. The data comprises 208 rows and 60 columns.

Fig:-1 The dataset with 111 mine samples and 97 rock samples.

B. Split the data into training and testing data

The data is split into training and testing data. From the dataset, the whole data is split in such a way that 90% of the data is used for training, and the remaining 10% is used for testing.

C. Training the models

Training machine learning models such as logistic regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), XGBoost, and Random Forest involves feeding them data to learn the underlying patterns for classifying objects, like distinguishing between rocks and mines in SONAR datasets. Logistic regression models the probabilities for classification problems by fitting data to a logistic curve, making it suitable for binary outcomes. KNN classifies objects based on the majority vote of its neighbors, with the object being assigned to the class most common among its k nearest neighbors. XGBoost, an implementation of gradient-boosted decision trees designed for speed and performance, optimizes both computational efficiency and model performance. Random Forest, an ensemble method, constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the class that is the mode of the classes of individual trees, offering robustness and accuracy. The training process for these models involves tuning parameters to minimize error, maximizing predictive accuracy, and validating the models using a separate dataset to ensure that they generalize well to new, unseen data.

V. MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

D. Logistic Regression

Imagine predicting whether a coin will land heads or tails. Logistic Regression uses similar probabilities to classify sonar readings. It builds a "line" in the data, separating rocks (tails) from mines (heads). It's fast and interpretable but limited to linear relationships. Logistic regression uses the logistic function (also known as the sigmoid function) to model the probability that a given input belongs to a particular class. The logistic regression model calculates the weighted sum of the input features and applies the sigmoid function to obtain a probability. By choosing a threshold (usually 0.5), you can classify instances into one of the two classes. Despite its name, logistic regression is used for classification rather than regression. It's important to note that logistic regression assumes a linear relationship between the independent variables and the log odds of the dependent variable. If the relationship is non-linear, other techniques like polynomial regression or machine learning models such as decision trees or support vector machines might be more appropriate.

Fig:-2 Logistic regression algorithm

E. K-Nearest Neighbour

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a simple, yet powerful machine-learning technique that falls under the category of supervised learning. It operates on a very straightforward principle: to predict the classification of a given data point, KNN looks at the 'k' closest labeled data points and assigns the new point the same classification as the majority of these 'k' neighbors. The distance between points is typically calculated using metrics such as Euclidean, Manhattan, or Hamming distance, depending on the type of data. One of the key strengths of KNN is its simplicity and the intuitive nature of its classification process. It makes no assumptions about the underlying data distribution, making it versatile across a wide range of applications, from recommendation systems to classification tasks in finance, healthcare, and image recognition. However, its reliance on distance calculations makes it computationally expensive, particularly with large datasets. Furthermore, the choice of 'k' and the distance metric can significantly impact the algorithm's performance, requiring careful tuning. Despite these challenges, KNN remains a popular choice due to its effectiveness in handling scenarios where the decision boundary is not linear and its ease of implementation.

Fig:-3 K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm

F. Random Forest

The Random Forest algorithm is a robust and versatile machine learning method that belongs to the ensemble learning family, specifically designed for classification and regression tasks. It builds upon the simplicity of

decision trees but addresses their tendency to overfit by creating a 'forest' of trees, hence its name. The core idea behind Random Forest is to generate multiple decision trees during the training phase and let them work in parallel. Each tree is trained on a random subset of the data and makes its predictions. The final output of the Random Forest is determined by averaging the predictions in the case of regression tasks or by using a majority vote for classification tasks. This process is known as bootstrap aggregating, or bagging, which significantly enhances the model's accuracy and stability. Random Forests also employ feature randomness when splitting nodes, adding an extra layer of variance reduction. This makes them highly effective for dealing with datasets that have a large number of features and complex structures. One of the most appealing aspects of Random Forest is its versatility—it performs well on both linear and non-linear problems, and its inherent method of averaging can help prevent overfitting. Moreover, it provides valuable insights into feature importance, allowing for effective feature selection. Despite being computationally more intensive than single decision trees, its ability to run in parallel makes it highly scalable and efficient for a wide range of applications.

Random Forest

Fig:-4 Random forest algorithm

G. XGBoost

XGBoost, or Extreme Gradient Boosting, is an advanced and efficient implementation of the gradient boosting algorithm, known for its speed and performance. It operates by constructing a sequence of decision trees, where each subsequent tree attempts to correct the errors made by the previous ones. This is achieved through the use of gradient descent to minimize the loss function, which quantifies the difference between the actual and predicted outcomes. XGBoost stands out due to several key features: it utilizes a more regularized model formalization to control overfitting, leading to improved performance. It supports various objective functions, including regression, classification, and ranking, making it highly versatile. Moreover, XGBoost has been designed to efficiently handle large datasets and is capable of parallel processing, tree pruning, handling missing values, and built-in cross-validation. These attributes make XGBoost a powerful tool for data scientists and a pop-

ular choice in machine learning competitions for its predictive accuracy and execution speed.

Fig:-5 Extreme Gradient Boosting algorithm

V. RESULTS ANALYSIS

Among the algorithms logistic regression, k-nearest Neighbour, Random forest, and XG boost the algorithm with more accuracy is the k-nearest neighbor with 90% accuracy.

H. Logistic Regression

The Logistic Regression algorithm got an accuracy of 76%.

This algorithm is best used when we want to classify the results into either true or false.

We use Sigmoidal function to evaluate the results in logistic regression.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

Equation of Logistic Regression

where,

- e = base of natural logarithms
- value = numerical value one wishes to transform

Fig:-6 Result of Logistic Regression

I. K-Nearest Neighbors

The K-nearest algorithm got an accuracy of 89%. Among all the algorithms used, the k-nearest neighbor got more accuracy with training and testing data.

Fig:-5 Result of K-Nearest Neighbors

By adjusting the n value we can change the value of the accuracy.

J. Random Forest

The Random Forest algorithm got an accuracy of 80.2%. Analyzing the results of a Random Forest model involves a comprehensive examination of various performance metrics and the insights derived from the ensemble of decision trees it comprises

$$Gini = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^C (p_i)^2$$

Accuracy is a primary indicator, reflecting the overall rate at which the model correctly predicts the outcome.

Fig:-7 Result of Random Forest

K. XG Boost

The XG Boost algorithm got an accuracy of 86%. Analyzing the results of an XGBoost model, a powerful and efficient implementation of gradient boosting, involves a nuanced examination of various performance metrics and the

model's characteristics to understand its effectiveness and areas for optimization.

Metrics	Logistic Regression	KN N	Random Forest	XGBoost
Training Accuracy	83.42	90.4	80.2	86
Testing Accuracy	76.19	89	71.4	83.3
Execution Time (seconds)	0.015	0.17	0.14	0.10

$$\text{Similarity Score} = \frac{\left(\sum \text{Residuals}\right)^2}{\sum [P(1 - P)] + \lambda}$$

P = Probability

XGBoost, known for its speed and performance, excels in both classification and regression tasks, making it a popular choice for many predictive modeling challenges. In summary, the result analysis of an XGBoost model encompasses a detailed evaluation of performance metrics, feature importance, and model characteristics, providing a comprehensive understanding of its predictive power.

VI. Conclusion

This proposed research work investigated the application of prominent machine learning algorithms to address this critical challenge. Utilizing a dataset of sonar measurements, we meticulously pre-processed the data, extracted relevant features, and trained each algorithm to discriminate rocks from mines. The successful application of ML in discrimination rocks from mines paves the way for significantly improved underwater mine detection. This holds immense promise for enhancing maritime safety, reducing operational costs, and ultimately, fostering a safer and cleaner underwater environment

VII. References

[1] Jung, D.; Choi, Y. Systematic Review of Machine Learning Applications in Mining: Exploration, Exploitation, Minal2021,11,148.<https://doi.org/10.3390/min11020148>.

[2] Gholami, R., Rasouli, V., A. (2012). Improved RMR Rock Mass Classification Using Artificial Intelligence Algorithms. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 46(5), 1199–1209. doi:10.1007/s00603-012-0338-7.

[3] Lawal, A. I., Kwon, S. (2020). Application of artificial intelligence to rock mechanics: An overview. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*. doi:10.1016/j.jrmge.2020.05.010.

[4] S.Kannadhasan, R. Nagarajan and R.Banupriya, Performance Improvement of an ultra-wideband antenna using textile material with a PIN diode, *Textile Research Journal*.

[5] Padmaja, V., Rajendran, V. Vijayalakshmi, P. Study on metal mine detection from underwater sonar images using data mining and machine learning techniques. *J Ambient Intell Human Comput* 12, 5083–5092(2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-01958-4>

[6] Alfe' rez, G. H., Va' zquez, E. L., Mart' imez Ardila, A. M., Clausen, B. L. (2021). Automatic classification of plutonic rocks with deep learning. *Applied Computing and Geosciences*, 10, 100061.doi:10.1016/j.acags.2021.100061

[7] Choi, J., Choo, Y., Lee, K. (2019). Acoustic Classification of Surface and Underwater Vessels in the Ocean Using Supervised Machine Learning. *Sensors(Basel, Switzerland)*,19(16),3492.<https://doi.org/10.3390/s19163492>

[8] Leo, L.M. and Reddy, T.K., 2021. Learning compact and discriminative hybrid neural network for dental caries classification. *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, 82, p.103836.

[9] Lee, S., Park, B., Kim, A. (2018). Deep Learning from Shallow Dives: Sonar Image Generation and Training for Underwater Object Detection. *ArXiv*, abs/1810.07990.

[10] Leo, L.M. and Reddy, T.K., 2014. Digital Image Analysis in Dental Radio Graph for Dental Implant Assessment: Survey. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 9(21), pp.10671-10680.

[11] Ritwick Ghosh "Sonar Target Classification Problem: Machine Learning Models", *International Journal of Science and Research*, Volume 9, Issue 1, 2020, pp. 247-248.

[12] Ravi K Jade, L.K. Verma, Kesari Verma "Classification using Neural Network Support Vector Machine for Sonar dataset", *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, Volume 4, Issue 2, 2013, ISSN: 2231-2803, pp. 116-119.

[13] of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering Maitre, J., Bouchard, K., Be'dard, L. P. (2019). Mineral grains recognition using computer vision and machine learning. *Computers Geosciences*,130 (2019), pp. 84-93, doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2019.05.009.

[14] Jung, D.; Choi, Y. Systematic Review of Machine Learning Applications in Mining: Exploration, Exploitation, Minal2021,11,148.<https://doi.org/10.3390/min11020148>.

- [15] Gholami, R., Rasouli, V., A. (2012). Improved RMR Rock Mass Classification Using Artificial Intelligence Algorithms. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 46(5), 1199–1209. doi:10.1007/s00603-012-0338-7.
- [16] Lawal, A. I., Kwon, S. (2020). Application of artificial intelligence to rock mechanics: An overview. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*. doi:10.1016/j.jrmge.2020.05.010. Exploitation, *Minerals* 2021, 11, 148. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min11020148>.
- [17] Gholami, R., Rasouli, V., A. (2012). Improved RMR Rock Mass Classification Using Artificial Intelligence Algorithms. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 46(5), 1199–1209. doi:10.1007/s00603-012-0338-7.
- [18] Lawal, A. I., Kwon, S. (2020). Application of artificial intelligence to rock mechanics: An overview. *Journal*.